

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis of Some New 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles

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In order to examine their hypoglycemic activity a series of 4-arylhydrazono-N'-arylthiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones has been synthesised and reported in a separate communication¹. The present report concerns the synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-arylthiocarbamoylpyrazoles(A).

The compounds described here have been synthesised by reacting 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones with different derivatives of phenylthiosemicarbazides. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental, ir and mass spectral studies. The reactivity of 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones was smooth and the products were obtained in good yield. The reactivity followed the expected course, diazonium chloride with electron withdrawing group in position 2 and 4 gave better yields. Colour of compounds ranges from yellow to orange.

Experimental

IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Beckmann I.R. spectrophotometer. Mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer. 2,3,4-Pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones were prepared by the reported method².

3,5-Dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles: 2,3,4-Pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazone (0.004 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (50 ml). A hot solution of phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.004 mol) in alcohol was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hrs. Shining crystals separated out on cooling which were recrystallised from 60% ethyl alcohol. Anal: m.p. 78°. Calculated for C₁₈H₁₇N₅S: N, 20.95%. Found: N, 20.7% $\nu^{(KBr)}$ 1600 cm⁻¹ (-N=N-), 3420 cm⁻¹ (-NH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=C or C=N) and 830-690 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl) λ_{max} CH₃OH 425 nm for -N=N- grouping, M⁺ at m/e 335.

Other 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles were prepared in the same way by taking suitably substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide and 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones and their characteristics are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 3,5-DIMETHYL-4-PHENYLAZO-N'-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYLPIRAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅	70%	78
2.	2-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	60%	121
3.	3-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	60%	184
4.	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	65%	129
5.	2-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	60%	125
6.	4-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	55%	96
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	50%	132
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	55%	116
9.	2-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	65%	110
10.	3-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	60%	108
11.	4-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	55%	103
12.	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	75%	176
13.	4-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	78%	210
14.	4-Br	C ₆ H ₅	65%	120
15.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	63%	125
16.	H	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65%	85
17.	2-Cl	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	118
18.	4-Cl	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65%	130
19.	2-CH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	113
20.	4-CH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	97
21.	2-OCH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50%	137
22.	4-OCH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	160
23.	2-NO ₂	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70%	148
24.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	200
25.	4-Br	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	125
26.	2,5(Cl) ₂	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	67%	124

All the compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

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